

The Intention and Reception of spatialisation: analysis, findings and discussion

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Abstract

Spatialisation always held a crucial importance in the acousmatic music practice, both live diffused through specialised instruments such as the Acousmonium, but also fixed, composed and crystallised onto a medium. The spatial qualities of a work have become even more important nowadays, with the rise of virtual reality technologies that highlight immersive experiences, or with new industrial standards for spatial audio in cinema (Sergi 2013). Nevertheless, the scholarship behind the use of spatialisation in acousmatic music is undoubtedly underdeveloped, with limited analytical output regarding the compositional use of this parameter, but also the musical reception of listeners – i.e. their spatial experience. This paper discusses the design, results and analysis of a novel iteration of the Intention/Reception project, originally developed by Landy and Weale (Weale 2006), but that focuses only on the interplay between spatialisation and listeners' reception. The main objective of this qualitative study is to gather information on how listeners interpret and experience spatialisation of multichannel acousmatic works. Data was analysed through the lenses of three main emerging thematic categories: spatial, extra-spatial and emotional. Experimental findings suggest listeners primarily engage with spatialisation in relation to sonic content of multichannel acousmatic music, but also that dramaturgic information can be impactful on both perception and reception of spatialisation. For composers employing multichannel formats and immersive audio systems, these insights confirm the significant implications of perceptual, formal and communicative aspects of spatialisation.

1. Introduction, background and context

The spatiality of sound has always been crucial in the musical practice: certain spaces were chosen as musical venues even in prehistoric eras (Boren 2017). The attention of composers to spatiality can be observed throughout music history: between the 14th and 17th century, for instance, the practices of *antiphonal psalms*, *polychoral style* and *cori spezzati* (Solomon 2007), defined the first documented (as in scored) instances of 'intentional' positioning and movement of materials through space, effectively spatialising sound. Mozart's *Notturmo for four Orchestras in D Major K. 286/269a* (1777) carefully used four orchestral groups in different locations to emulate movement and echo effects; Giuseppe Verdi's *Requiem* (1874) employed off-stage trumpets to create a distance effect, similarly to the strings in Charles Ives' *The Unanswered Question* (1908). This attention to spatialisation increased dramatically after the Second World War, with instrumentals works by composers such as Stockhausen

(e.g. *Gruppen* in 1955, *Carrè* in 1960), Xenakis (e.g. *Terretektorh* in 1966, *Persephassa* in 1969), Brant, Schafer and many more (Zvonar 2004). However, it is thanks to the electronic medium that spatialisation increasingly became integral in the compositional practice. The pioneering work of Schaeffer and Henry (*potentiomètre d'espace*), the later introduction of the Acousmonium by François Bayle for the diffusion of Acousmatic music (DeSantos et al. 1997), Chowning studies on digital reverberation and psychoacoustic cues in electroacoustic composition (Chowning 1977), the introduction of Ambisonics (Zotter and Frank 2019) and modern HDLA's (High Density Loudspeaker Arrays) were crucial in diversifying spatialisation approaches and enlarging the possibilities of composers for placing, diffusing and moving sounds in space. This shows that the technical and technological applications of spatialisation are one of the most active research fields. However, it also highlights the lack of scholarship surrounding spatialisation, with very few studies on its musicology and listeners' understanding. The Intention/Reception project by Landy and (Weale 2006) is used to study the relationship between what a listener receives and interprets musically and the intention of the composer. The first instance of the project concentrated on the 'something to hold on to factors' (Landy 1994), a list of parameters that Landy identifies as potential 'hooks' for listeners while experiencing timbral composition. This list is expanded by Weale during this first instance of the project and encompasses a broad spectrum of categories relating to timbral composition. The project consists of several questionnaires given to listeners, both during and after the listening of the works. These are called Real-Time Questionnaires (RTQ) and Directed Questionnaires (DQ), which are later compared to a Composer's Intention Questionnaire (CIQ), useful in gathering dramaturgic information from the composers themselves. The study concerns on the question of *why* something happens, its context and communicative power: this concept is called dramaturgy. As such, dramaturgy is understood to be information that a composer may offer to a listener for them to better understand the musical work. This study is a part of the PhD of the author, which can be seen in the graph in fig. 1, representing the various blocks of the research project.

This Intention/Reception study is one of two parts of a mixed methodology designed to gather useful qualitative data on the spatial experience of musical works, aimed at the development of a framework for the analysis of spatialisation and a vocabulary of signs for its description.

Figure 1, functional interconnections of the PhD project of the author. Intention/Reception questionnaires on left hand side, as part of the methodology

2. Intention/Reception for spatialisation

The Intention/Reception project can be adapted to different musical genres or to fit a specific need: the design of the questionnaires defines the aims of the project. For instance, Andrew Knight-Hill proposes to study audience interpretations of electroacoustic audio-visual music through a three-phase Intention/Reception project, where results from each phase would inform a process of adaptation and recomposition of new works (Hill 2013). This demonstrates the flexibility and adaptability of this particular methodology. In fact, one of the original parameters of the 'something to hold on to' factor is 'space' (Landy 1994), later redefined as 'spatiality' by Weale (Weale 2006). It is possible, consequently, to redesign the original Intention/Reception project to investigate the topic of spatialisation, narrowing its focus to this single parameter. However, it is not the aim of this project to create a new or revised version of the original methodology, but rather to make use of its strength and flexibility in the context of this research. Regardless, the original structure of the questionnaires is kept, with certain adjustments, such as limiting the number of listening sessions (from three to two) to avoid listening fatigue for inexperienced listeners or the specific nature of the questions, aim at soliciting specific qualitative data.

2.1. Structure of the questionnaires and tests

As per the original Intention/Reception project, two questionnaires are developed: the Composer's Intention Questionnaire (CIQ) and the Listener's Reception Questionnaire (LRQ). While the former is designed to extrapolate useful dramaturgic information and as a comparison to understand whether such dramaturgic information impacts listeners' reception, the latter are specifically aimed at listeners. The LRQ are divided into three sections:

- A first Real-Time Questionnaire (RTQ-1) where no information about the composition is provided to the listeners. During this first listening session the participants can freely write down their thoughts, images or feelings regarding the spatial aspects the composition as they experience it.
- A second Real-Time Questionnaire (RTQ-2) where dramaturgic information solicited through the CIQ are presented to the listeners, such as the title of the work, programme notes, compositional inspiration etc... Again, during this listening session the participants are encouraged to write down any images, feelings or any changed thought from the first listening session.
- A Directed Questionnaire (DQ) presented to the listeners after the second listening session, designed to solicit more in-depth information regarding the spatial experience of the work. This questionnaire encourages the participants to expand and provide further details from the RTQs. The DQs, with eight questions in total, are further divided into three sections, addressing different aspects of listeners' experience:
 - DQ from 1 to 3: impact, meaning and understanding of perceived spatial events.
 - DQ from 4 to 6: narrative, structure and sonic qualities of spatial events.
 - DQ 7 and 8: reception and appreciation of spatial event.

The questionnaires were designed to provide data concerning:

- The extent to which the listeners make sense of and appreciate the spatial aspects of the work, both from its content alone and with the aid of dramaturgic information.
- The spatial categories or shapes that are received or understood as musically relevant by the listeners, if any.
- The extent to which the spatialisation and other musical parameters (such as rhythm, pitch, or timbre) are contextualised and interconnected by the listeners.
- The extent to which listeners understand a formal musical function of spatialisation.

The solicited qualitative data from these questionnaires are then compared with the information provided by the composer's intention questionnaire, to find any useful correlations, confirmations or contrasts.

2.2. Participants

Participation in the listening tests was on a completely voluntary and informed basis. Participants, fifteen in total, ranged from 25 to 60 years old and resided either in Italy (10/15 or 66%) or the United Kingdom (5/15 or 33%). The most important aspect considered was the level of expertise, particularly with spatial audio, which was also used as a scale to measure that participants were equally represented. The selection of respondents was done to avoid selection bias and systematic differences between groups and group responses. The aim was to balance between experienced and inexperienced participants plus those who identify as having 'some experience'. Moreover, this choice was mainly made to circumvent two more problems:

- avoid expertise bias. Experienced listeners generally have better analytical listening skills or domain-specific biases. Inexperienced listeners tend to rely on more intuitive, everyday listening. A balanced combination of both helps to avoid biased outcomes that favour one group's listening habits.
- avoid over-sensitivity in responses. Experienced listeners may be overly critical, noticing subtle details that most people would overlook. Inexperienced participants provide a more typical real-world perspective, focusing on aspects that may be more readily apparent. A balance would prevent any bias towards one or the other approach.

Participants with a no knowledge of electroacoustic music, spatial audio or music technology in general were considered 'inexperienced'; composers, practitioners and academics were considered 'experienced'; participants with some knowledge of spatial audio, video game sound design, cinema production and similar were categorised as having 'some knowledge'. The focus of the study was the quality of the individual listeners' spatial experience and their personal interpretations and descriptions. In particular, the inexperienced listeners (and marginally those with 'some experience') provided more natural and intuitive responses, balancing the more formal and attentive responses of the experienced group. This equilibrium was achieved by including 7 experienced listeners (46%), 6 inexperienced listeners (40%) and 2 listeners (13%) that declared 'some experience' with spatial audio.

2.3. Choice of compositions

The original Intention/Reception project employed three compositions with very different characteristics:

- *ABZ/A* by Pete Stollery, a location soundscape work with little to no manipulation of the material.
- *Deep Pockets* by Larisa Montanaro, a soundscape work with some abstracted and transformed sounds, exploring some of their musicality but keeping their sonic identity recognisable.
- *Nocture* by Simon Atkinson, where the sound content is so manipulated and abstracted that any real-world reference is absent.

In this project, two original acousmatic compositions created by the author during the research period are used for the listening tests. Both compositions are similar in structure and duration, approximately 7'20" for *A House in the Storm*, and 8'09" for *Travelling Without Moving*. Moreover, the two pieces also share a similar spatialisation thinking, designed to explore different spatial behaviours within a fixed media format. This consistency provided a controlled experimental context while allowing for different variation in spatial morphologies and behaviours to be tested. This relatively short duration avoids listening fatigue during the repeated listening ensures that participants remain focused throughout the experience, an essential aspect for capturing detailed and reliable responses. The two compositions present several key differences, and these contrasts offer useful insights into how listeners receive and interpret spatialisation under different conditions:

- *A House in the Storm* (2022) features a variety of recognisable sound sources and spatial textures. Sounds such as a lighter and the subsequent lighting of a cigarette, footsteps, doors opening and closing, wood creaks and the complex texture of wind, resembling the storm, are clearly part of the structure of the piece.
- *Travelling Without Moving* (2023), instead, includes a wider range of abstract sound sources. The sound materials are heavily modified and less recognisable, ambiguous and open to interpretation. The absence of obvious referential cues offers the listeners a more personal interpretative experience, where aspects such as the relationship between spatial and sonic behaviours emerges through perceptual association rather than being influenced by self-evident cues. This ambiguity invites a more active role from the listener, who in turn provides useful qualitative data on their interpretation and reception of spatialisation in highly abstract sound contexts.

The juxtaposition of these two compositional approaches --- one grounded in recognisable source bonding, the other in abstraction and ambiguity --- is strategically valuable for the research, since it allows for a comparison of how the relationships between the recognition of sound and spatialisation are received, processed, and interpreted by listeners.

Both compositions are available online as a binaural reduction¹ or requested privately to the author, who will send the 8-channel versions of the works with appropriate layout information.

2.4. Managing variables in the listening tests

Multichannel acousmatic music is becoming increasingly diversified, both from an aesthetic and technological perspective. In (Peters et al. 2011) it is shown that composers (not only of acousmatic music) used several speakers arrangements such as 5.1, 7.1, octophonic or even

¹ <https://soundcloud.com/stefanocatena>

composed for larger multichannel systems. Inevitably, this difference in loudspeaker layout leads to a variety of compositions that may not be suitable for all multichannel systems. This can create a lack of coherence in the listening experience depending on the piece played, leading to unreliable results. In recent years this differentiation has become even broader, thanks to new technologies and their increased accessibility and low cost.

In the case of the listening tests, acoustics also play a significant role. Acousmatic music is commonly played in a variety of venues: from concert halls to treated listening rooms. However, acoustics can also interfere with the correct reproduction of multichannel acousmatic music. Minimising these problems is essential to maintain coherence and alignment in my listening tests, ensuring that all participants experience the same conditions for reliable and unbiased results. To guarantee this, practical choices were made ahead of the listening tests:

- only eight-channel fixed acousmatic works were employed. The chosen works are both composed by the author and while made with Ambisonics technology, they are perfectly suitable for eight-channel reproduction.
- the chosen locations for the listening tests are treated eight-channel capable studios. The main studio used is De Montfort's 'Diffusion Studio', Clephan Building, Multichannel Studio (CL 00.16), De Montfort University, Leicester LE1 9BH; furthermore, the private studio of the author was employed, which features an eight-channel diffusion system and an acoustically treated space.

3. Analysis and approach

Thematic analysis was used to interpret the qualitative data that was gathered from the listening questionnaires. Both RTQs and DQs were investigated qualitatively, coding the responses, terminology and vocabulary to identify emerging themes and patterns. The Real-Time Questionnaires were intended to capture participants' immediate reactions during listening experiences, documenting their reception of spatialisation as music unfolded. The Directed Questionnaires were structured to encourage more focused responses on specific aspects of the listening experience, asking participants to reflect on parameters such as the impact, meaning and understanding of spatialisation, narrative and structural sonic qualities of spatial events and their reception and appreciation. The responses have been translated by the researcher as accurately as possible to avoid any misrepresentation of the data itself. Thematic analysis was employed to investigate the qualitative data, evaluating meaningful terminology and listeners' vocabulary, and creating a set of 'themes' to address the project's core research questions. These themes are useful for the interpretation of the listeners' responses, identifying patterns of meaning within the qualitative data.

Original scans with handwritten responses (both English and Italian) and translations are freely available on FigShare².

² <https://figshare.com/s/3fdb9b7083d70994dbe8>

3.1. Emerging themes and patterns

The analytical process shown three main thematic categories: spatial, extra-spatial and emotional. These refer to how listeners verbalised their thoughts during the tests, what they interpreted while experiencing the spatialisation of the works, and overall images, correlations and descriptions.

- **Spatial:** this category refers strictly to the received spatial qualities of the sound, focusing on aspects such as immersion and envelopment, movement and placement. Responses that fall under this theme describe how spatialisation functions as a primary perceptual dimension, shaping the listener's awareness of spatial qualities of sound without necessarily attributing extramusical meaning.
- **Extra-spatial:** this theme extends beyond spatialisation itself and considers how listeners contextualize spatial events within a broader sonic and narrative framework. It accounts for the way spatial qualities of sound interact with other musical and sonic material, such as spectromorphology and event sequencing, to form a cohesive listening experience. The extra-spatial dimension reflects how spatialisation contributes to perceived structure, musical or non-musical storytelling, often correlating movements and placements to an underlying sense of progression or intention within the musical work.
- **Emotional:** this theme addresses the affective responses elicited by the spatial events as they unfold during the musical work. Listeners may describe feelings of tension, excitement, fear, calmness or expectation in response to spatial movements and placements. These reactions highlight an emotional impact of the spatial events, demonstrating how spatialisation can enhance the musical experience and its appreciation.

3.2. Analysis of questionnaires: “A House in the Storm”

3.2.1. RTQ-1 (without dramaturgic information)

Most listeners (80%) have listed thoughts, images or feelings strongly related with the spectromorphological content of the work (extra-spatial theme). Many were able to correctly assume the nature and intent of the work based on the sonic material, such as the ‘storm’, as an important part of the work's narrative. Participants were also able to consistently identify the used concrete sounds: 60% perceived and described a house, footsteps, a doorbell, wood or a cigarette. A smaller percentage of listeners (26%) have focused their responses more on spatialisation and spatial aspects (spatial theme), contextualising them into the narrative of the work or with their spectromorphological content, such as sounds having ‘low directionality’ or discussing the immersion within the spatial scene.

The vocabulary used throughout the responses also provides interesting information. Most of listeners (93%) have employed terms and phrases that implicitly or explicitly imply either a sense of motion or immersion:

- **spatial movement and directionality:** the use of words such as moving, shifting, escaping, approaching, entering, falling, fleeing, following, cascading, rotating, circular or spiralling suggest that listeners are aware of dynamic positioning and

motion of the sounds during the work. Terms like moving, shifting or cascading indicate smooth, continuous movements, whereas escaping, following, approaching imply directed or intentional motion. Circular, spiralling, rotating imply a perception of sound moving around the listener, also suggesting smooth movement, but also implying a specific trajectory and motion morphology.

- spatial placement, diffusion and envelopment: the use of words such as within, inside, close, distant, foreground, background, open, enclosed, narrow, wide, immersive, enveloping, diffused, spread, and surround indicate awareness of sound positioning and listener perspective, but also how sound fills or interacts with the 3D sound scene.

3.2.1. RTQ-2 (with dramaturgic information)

After having provided dramaturgic information and the second listening session, most of participants still strongly refer the spatialisation of sound with its spectromorphological content and relative narrative of the work. 40% explicitly stated that the dramaturgic information has helped them better understand the work, even partially, or has confirmed their expectations and responses from the first listening. The emotional response is still present, but it is now less focused on the feelings themselves but is rather contextualised within the domain of the work. After reading the dramaturgic information, they have contextualised the evoked feelings within the narrative of the work, also including vocabulary that explicitly refers to spatial motions: e.g. 'movement of trees around the house', 'being dragged away', 'collapse'. The vocabulary used in the responses remains quite similar from the previous listening. Words such as walking, movement, dragged away, collapsing, approaching, chasing and journey refer to concepts of spatial motions. Words such as immersion, foreground, background, surrounding, creaking, sounds everywhere, all-encompassing, envelopment refer to spatial placements and diffusion. Differently from the first listening, participants have given more specific information on the perceived 'place' of the work.

3.2.2. DQ-1

The directed questionnaires show a very clear indicators of listeners' reception. The extra-spatial responses are overwhelmingly present throughout the questionnaires, suggesting that the listeners relate more to the sonic material narrative and structural aspects. This is more visible in DQs 4-6 and DQs 7-8. DQ-1.8 only presents extra-spatial responses to highlight this even more. Purely spatial responses are also very present, mostly in DQs 1-4, which were the group of questions on the impact of spatial events. However, they decrease steadily as the extra-spatial group emerges in the latter questions. Emotional responses are quite low, except DQ-1.5, but this was expected from the design of the questionnaires. Clearly, the graph shows data that can exceed 100% of the responses: this is because on response can be include multiple thematic categories (e.g. be both spatial and extra-spatial).

Figure 2: grouped bar chart represent overall percentages of every thematic category per question in DQ-1

3.2.3. Comparing intention and reception

The first listening interpretations of *A House in the Storm* have focused strongly on both spatial and extra-spatial qualities that participants have received during the experience. Even without dramaturgic information, several listeners have correctly understood the nature of the overall sonic environment on a spatial, spectral, emotional and narrative level. A key aspect of the reception of the composer's intentions is the choice of specific words and terminology used by the listeners, as analysed in the previous sections. The terms 'storm' or 'stormy', for instance, were present in 33% (5/15) of the responses, even when the respondents did not know the title of the piece. While this aspect is extra-spatial, relating to the overall sonic material used in the first section of the piece, it also refers to the enveloping and fast paced movements of sounds present. Overall, the percentage of the listeners that have correctly identified some spatial or extra spatial features of the work in RTQ-1 is 60% (9/15). On the emotional category, instead, the listeners that have indicated an implicit or explicit emotional response that matches the composer's intention as indicated in CIQ-1 is 40% (6/15).

After the presentation of the dramaturgic information to the listeners, responses on the extra-spatial theme have changed significantly. As expected, the title played an important role in 'guiding' the listeners into understanding the compositional intent: while in RTQ-1.1 only 13% (2/15) of the responses indicated a 'house' or similar, in RTQ-1.2 this percentage reached 53% (8/15). Similarly to RTQ-1.1, the mentions of 'storm' or its descriptions were present at 33% (5/15), rising to 53% (8/15) in RTQ-1.2. By understanding extra-spatial features such as 'storm' and 'house' in this work, listeners also contextualise the spatial aspects that follow: the house represents static and a sense of 'place', while the storm symbolises movement,

envelopment and dynamism. The dramaturgic information was also described by several responses to have changed or helped the overall understanding of the work, either sonically or on a narrative level.

3.3. Analysis of questionnaires: “Travelling without moving”

3.3.1. RTQ-1 (without dramaturgic information)

Similarly to the first acousmatic work, participants favoured responses that strongly linked spectral content with their spatial behaviour, trying to develop and contextualise a narrative of the work. 73% of listeners have described or identified sonic properties of sound, framing them within the work's context or detailing them with explicit spatial properties, again describing a sense of 'place' in the composition. The natural elements and environments were also consistently recognized by the participants. Water-related imagery such as 'rainy section', 'trickle of water', 'water running all around' or 'water suggests a cave' involve the diffused feeling of water enveloping the participants. Most listeners (86%) have perceived that the movement is a crucial part of the work and used a term that directly refer to spatial motion. Words such as rotary or rotatory, spinning, travelling, flying, hovering, speed, escape trajectory, motion, running, or 'gets closer and then away', all concern different types of spatial movements that were perceived in the composition. The emotional responses in this work are mixed and generally fewer than the previous: participants favoured a narrative and contextual response. A smaller percentage of participants have given more importance to spatialisation (26%). They have provided more detailed analysis of their spatial perception of the work, without consistently indicating sonic properties, spectromorphologies or even a narrative context.

3.3.2. RTQ-2 (with dramaturgic information)

Again, participants strongly used sonic qualities to describe their reception of spatial events and the narrative of the work. 66% of the listeners linked spectral content with spatial behaviour: 'ferry engines, birds flying, dragged metals, steam train in motion, a shower'. Several listeners stated how the dramaturgic information changed their reception of the work, both on a narrative and spatial perspective. The first impressions of travelling, flying, hovering and trajectories are confirmed in this second session, being re-stated by most of the participants; to quote a listener, they assert that 'the "journey" aspect confirmed my first impressions'.

3.3.3. DQ-2

DQ-2 is similar to DQ-1, showing that the extra-spatial responses are prominent throughout all the questions, with an overwhelming majority in DQ-2.1, DQ-2.6 and DQ-2.7. However, the purely spatial theme is also strongly present, especially in the first four questions. This suggests that the impact that *Travelling Without Moving* had on the listeners was very focused on the meta-motion of the material, thanks to its abstract nature. *Travelling Without Moving* does not provide any precise reference, nor does its dramaturgic information. 'Motion', 'movement' or 'travel' are abstract notions that leave more room for interpretation to the listeners, leading again to a very extra-spatial oriented responses throughout the

questionnaires. Again, the emotional response is still present but quite low, with a peak at 46% in the responses in DQ-2.5.

Figure 3: grouped bar chart represent overall percentages of every thematic category per question in DQ-2

3.3.4. Comparing intention and reception

Travelling Without Moving, compared to the previous work, provides fewer strongly recognisable sonic materials, but rather includes synthesised and heavily modified sounds. The lack of immediately recognisable sources is done purposefully with the intent of stimulating listener's imagination on both the spectral and spatial levels. The work's focus is the concept of spatial movement, as detailed in CIQ-2.1: the composer wants to 'communicate the sense of nostalgia of a distant home through "moving" sound'. Furthermore, in CIQ-2.3 and CIQ-2.4 the composer describes that the concept of travel is a central theme of the composition, sonically and spatially.

During the first listening session, most of the participants (80%, 12/15) have either directly used words or terms describing motion and travel or described images and sounds that have an unequivocal connection to those concepts. Many listeners used words such as 'rotary', 'spinning' or 'flying', illustrating the reception of rotating or passing sonic movements. These references are clearly pointing towards the concept of motion and movement, but also to the idea of the composer of travel, going from one place to another onto a means of transport. Listeners also link the movement of sound with plausible spectral qualities or a sense of place and location, even though these may not be the composer's intention: for instance, the use of words such as 'airplanes', 'objects passing over' or 'train movements' are indicative. It is reasonable to state that the composer also wants to express an emotional state with the work.

However, the responses present in RTQ-2.1 do not reflect the 'nostalgia' feeling that work is supposed to convey. The emotional response is quite low, sitting at 20% (3/15).

The title and dramaturgy of the work have increased even more the perception of motion and movement in the work. While their presence in RTQ-2.1 was already at 80% (12/15), it now went up to 93% (14/15). This was expected, since both title and dramaturgic information guide the listeners towards movement and travelling, and most of the work is based on the spatial motions of sound. Similarly to RTQ-2.1, one of the most recurring terms is 'flying' or 'to fly', appearing in 40% (6/15) of the responses: this refers to both the 'travelling' aspect of the work, but also hinting at nature, also specified by the composer in CIQ-2.5. The participants also include an extra-spatial detail to the perception of flight, using words such as 'birds' or even 'helicopters'. By analysing the extra-spatial qualities of the responses, it is also clear that the dramaturgic information has been helpful for the listeners in contextualising the sounds with the composer's intentions. Terms referring to means of transport, for instance, have increased from 26% (4/15) in RTQ-2.1 to 46% in RTQ-2.2.

4. Discussion

The Real-Time Questionnaires (RTQ) have provided a rich and substantial amount of qualitative data describing the reception of spatialisation by the listeners during the experience itself. The analysis of the first real-time questionnaires (RTQ-1.1 and RTQ-2.1) indicate several key findings. The spectral and narrative qualities of the work are again of primary importance, with listeners linking spatial behaviour to sound, perceived and evoked images or structural aspects. In both *A House in the Storm* and in *Travelling Without Moving*, respondents have strongly referred to spectromorphology of sound. This indicates that it is the sounds themselves that helped the listeners enjoy and appreciate the spatial qualities of the work. Many listeners implicitly illustrate how the hierarchy of first reception can be described sequentially as 'sound-then-space'. While they were explicitly asked to 'list any thoughts, images or feelings that come to mind as you listen to the spatial placement of the sounds and their movement', still most have totally or partially described the sonic qualities of the work. These qualities, however, can be traced back to spatialisation aspects related to the work: in *Travelling Without Moving*, for instance, several listeners have described 'flying objects', 'birds' or 'wings flapping', which are clearly related to sound movements; or 'rainy' and 'granular textures' which are instead referring to envelopment and immersion. Similarly, in *A House in the Storm*, the most frequent term is 'door' or 'doorbell': this clear sonic reference traces back to the spatial placement of a doorbell sound, statically positioned (as if the listener was ringing it) in the front of the listening space.

RTQ-1.2 and 2.2 include responses influenced by the dramaturgic information, such as the title, programme note etc. Many listeners, in both works, still predominantly use extra-spatial characteristics to describe spatial aspects of the compositions. However, the dramaturgic information 'guides' the listening experience in some way and, as expected, the responses turned out to be more in line with the composer's intentions. While *A House in the Storm* is more explicit with its references, both spatially and sonically, *Travelling Without Moving* intentions have been still received correctly, with a degree of freedom within the interpretations, mostly on the sound materials and their origin. Still, these interpretations led to the intended results: the notions of 'travel', 'journey', 'nature' and 'movement' were all received and decoded by the listeners, as shown in RTQ-2.2.

By looking at the summaries of the directed questionnaire's data in figures 2 and 3 there are very clear indicators of listeners' reception in both works. While these graphs show data quantitatively and not qualitatively, they are useful in portraying how the emerged themes and patterns are present throughout the responses. It is quite apparent how the extra-spatial category is predominant in both DQ-1 and DQ-2 questionnaires. The listeners' responses are strongly focused on attributes of the work relating to their sonic matter, their narrative or structural aspects. The presence of extra-spatial content is the highest within the last two sets of questions (DQ 4-6 and DQ 7-8) regarding narrative, structure and sonic qualities of spatial events and their reception and appreciation. This indicates that the extra-spatial qualities of spatialisation in the acousmatic works are the primary elements received by the audience, influencing also how they understand and appreciate the purely spatial qualities. For instance, in both directed questionnaires, the extra-spatial content of the responses never went below 53%. Moreover, a large portion of the extra-spatial responses referred to sonic material and their meta-motion (Lewis 2010), rather than only addressing their explicit spatial movements, placement or perceived location. On the other hand, the data shows that there is also a crucial link between spatial and extra-spatial themes. In both directed questionnaires from DQ-1 to DQ-4, the purely spatial theme reaches over 60% of presence, together with a strong component of extra-spatial responses. The two data sets for the directed questionnaires show similar trends across all questions. The spatial theme is substantially represented within the first four questions, decreasing significantly in DQ 5-8. The extra-spatial theme is present constantly throughout all questions, with an overwhelming majority of presence in DQ-1.4-8, in DQ-2.1 and DQ-2.5-8. In DQ-2.1, instead, the extra-spatial content is much higher than DQ-1.1, 93% versus 66%. This suggests that the impact that *Travelling without Moving* had on the listeners was more focused on the meta-motion of the material and its influence on spatialisation rather than in *A House in the Storm*. Finally, the emotional response is also very similar in both questionnaires. They follow the same trend with only minor differences, for instance in DQ-1.8 and DQ-2.8, with 0% presence in the former and 26% in the latter, the largest difference observable in the questionnaires. The peak quantity of emotional content can be seen in DQ-1.5 and DQ-2.5, where the overall responses reach 46%. DQ 5 regards perceived feelings, meanings or images that spatial movements and placements experience may evoke, making this result predictable and expected.

By investigating listeners' vocabulary, it is also possible to extrapolate relevant information regarding the three emerged thematic categories that have emerged from the study.

- **Spatial:** this thematic category represents the reception of the morphology of spatial movements, placements and overall sense of directionality and localisation of sound. Both real-time and directed questionnaires have provided useful information regarding listeners' interpretation of these morphologies, contextualising them inside the larger compositional structure and the relevant sonic qualities of the work. The clearest finding observable is the explicit and substantial differentiation between immersion and movement. Listeners will discriminate between the very specific sound motion, wherever they are perceived, and a more generic sense of immersion into the sound itself. This implicitly confirms the thesis from Schumacher (Schumacher et al. 2022), where listeners do not receive, perceive or track complex spatial trajectories, only understanding overall characteristics of spatial motion or diffusion.
- **Extra-spatial:** this thematic category is unquestionably the most present in both real-time and directed questionnaires. It represents how listeners receive, connect and correlate the spatial qualities of the work with its sonic material, narrative arc and

formal structure. The most revealing questions are undoubtedly DQ 4 to 6, specifically designed to elicit qualitative extra-spatial data from the listeners. However, throughout all the directed questionnaires participants have been challenged in describing their spatial reception, and most of the time they have included extra-spatial information in these descriptions. Therefore, the main finding here is that listeners interpret spatial movements and placements together with their extra-spatial features, contextualising spatialisation and spatial behaviour with sonic materials or narrative aspects.

- **Emotional:** this thematic category is undoubtedly the least represented overall. From the directed questionnaires, for instance, is very clear how the emotional thematic category is the least represented, which is expected given the highly focused nature of the questions towards spatialisation. However, many listeners have indicated their feelings, emotions, expectations and subjective sensations regarding spatialisation in the two works.

5. Conclusions

This paper shows a report of useful qualitative data derived from an Intention/Reception project iteration aimed at studying listeners' experience of spatialisation in multichannel acousmatic music. The Intention/Reception project, originally developed by Landy/Weale, involves several rounds of listening of acousmatic music, with real-time and direct questionnaires presented to the respondents, studying changes in response upon the presentation of contextual dramaturgic information provided by the composer. In this iteration of the Intention/Reception project, two Real-Time Questionnaires (RTQs) are presented to the listeners, with and without dramaturgic information, alongside a Directed Questionnaire (DQ) after the listening sessions. The two chosen works *A House in the Storm* and *Travelling Without Moving* were used to evoke and paint a variety of spatial settings to extract a diverse range of responses. Overall, three main categories of answers are present constantly throughout the questionnaires:

- **Spatial:** responses that focus on the purely spatial aspects of the works, with words such as 'moving', 'enveloping', 'location', 'trajectory' etc.
- **Extra-spatial:** responses that extend beyond the purely spatial aspects of the works, including, for instance, spectromorphological or narrative qualities.
- **Emotional:** responses that address affective responses provoked by the work's spatial qualities.

The extra-spatial theme is predominant throughout the responses of both works. By examining the answers and analysing the use of vocabulary, it becomes apparent that aspects such as the spectromorphology of the spatial events or their related narrative are of primary importance. This is closely followed by the spatial responses, where listeners indicate their experience of any spatial movement or sound localisation within the works. Finally, the emotional category is the least represented in the questionnaires, indicating that while spatialisation can evoke a certain affective response, this may not be easily received by the listeners.

These findings suggest that composers must be aware of the connection that listeners create between these three thematic categories regarding spatialisation, and that exploiting listeners' reception to achieve their musical goal may be more fruitful than focusing on perceptually inaccessible technological tools.

6. Ethical statement

The Intention/Reception project is research that involves several listening tests and human subjects. Ethical approval from De Montfort's University Leicester Media School has been obtained before the beginning of the listening tests. Subjects were provided with informed consent forms, assured of confidentiality and given the chance to withdraw from the study at any time, which all of them signed.

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